

CRITICAL THINKING AND CURRICULUM MODIFICATION AS STRATEGIES FOR ERADICATING EXAMINATION MALPRACTICE IN NIGERIA'S EDUCATION SYSTEM

BY

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of critical thinking and curriculum modification as medium of eradicating examination malpractice in Nigeria educational system. The study employed survey research design. The research instrument adapted for the study were Titled critical thinking and curriculum modification as medium of eradicating examination malpractice in Nigeria educational system Rating Scale (CTCMEMNES). The sample for the study comprises of 317 lecturers in various higher institutions of learning in Nigeria. Cronbach's Alpha was used for the reliability and the coefficient $r=0.83$. The purposive sampling techniques procedures was adopted for the study. The data use for was analyzed using ANCOVA. Three hypotheses was postulated and tested at 0.05 significant level. The finding revealed that there was a significant influence of critical thinking on examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system. ($F_{(2, 23)} = 52.171$; $p>0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = .228$). It also revealed that curriculum modification was significantly predict examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system. ($F_{(1, 24)} = .705$; $p>0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = .004$). It also revealed teachers and parents' involvement on examination malpractice in Nigeria education system is significant. ($F_{(2, 23)} = 32.546$; $p>0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = .155$). The conclusion and recommendation follow.

Key Words: Examination Malpractice and Curriculum modification

Introduction

Education is a medium to achieve vibrant economic development in all stages of economic sectors whereas failure to embark on proper curriculum planning leveraging critical thinking affect economic growth of a nation (Abulencia, 2021). Critical thinking is a process of ammonizing modalities, configuring patterns and synthesizing ideas to solve existing problems (Abdurrahman, Setyaningsih, & Jalmo, 2019). Nigeria educational system had been truncated to the extent that both students learn, their critical thinking level had been eroded due to failure of providing enabling environment for learning process. Teachers and curriculum planners failed to design and implement curriculum that enhance technology development (Dewi, & Mashami, 2019).

Odebode (2021) opines that teachers input to curriculum development up to the implementation stage are instrumental to stimulate students learning process. A well design curriculum prepared students to attain relevant knowledge to withstand assessments and evaluation. The Western education system employed assessments and evaluation to determining the degree of which certain desirable changes in behaviour have actually taken place and as well an instrument used to decide students next academic level before certification. Deak, & Tanama, (2021) sees examination is an assessment tool upon which educational system revolves. It is an instrument used to decide student's levels of attainment in academic world. But it is unfortunate that examination which were meant to access student's strengths and

weaknesses lack credibility due to examination malpractice.

Examination malpractice is the order of the day in Nigeria educational system, it is a misconduct emanated from primary schools, secondary schools and tertiary institutions and encouraged by teachers, proprietors and some staffs of the examination bodies. Consider WAEC, NECO and JAMB examination in Nigeria, there are persistence records of examination malpractice every year. Irwanto, & Prodjosantoso, (2019) opines examination malpractice can be traced to students inability to think critically and inability of curriculum planners to design technology embraced curriculum. The curriculum that was design for decades were still in used till today, the curriculum is no more taking care of the what it need to make our educational sector compete with the advanced world because schools, colleges and universities that were established for the purpose of preparing students to be self-reliance, to determine the wealth of the nation and to explore nation resources to grow the nation economic lack creativity skills (Nurkholis, Miarsyah, &Indrayanti, 2018).

Nigeria students had been familiar with the paths leading to various methods of examination irregularity. In most cases some parents are so desperate to the extent of bribing their way through for the success of their own children and self-gratification. The fear of not been promoted or given admission for further study also prompt some students to engage in examination malpractice (Shirazi & Heidari, 2019). Although our curriculum do not accommodate revolutionized teaching and learning process where digital and technological know-how have been put in place for classroom instruction

The contribution of some teachers in our institutions of learning to examination

malpractice is very conspicuous, students at time bribe their way before and during examination so that they might be allow to engage in examination malpractice. Some tag this act perpetrated by the concern teachers as the consequent of level of poverty ravaging the nation (Twiningsih & Elisanti, 2021). Despite the teachers involvement in examination malpractice it is unfortunate that majority of students with distinctions in mathematics, physics, biology, chemistry, further mathematics could not cope after been admitted in to university. Even those one that manage to graduate found wanting in various field of their specialization. The fact that they obtain their certificates through malpractice prevent their functionality in the society which in turn affect the economic, political and social aspect of our nation.

Statement of the Problem

Examination malpractice has become a pervasive issue in Nigeria’s education system, undermining the validity and reliability of assessments, and compromising the quality of education. Despite efforts to curb the menace, it remains a significant challenge, threatening the very fabric of the education sector. The traditional approach to teaching and learning, coupled with an inflexible curriculum, contributes to the prevalence of examination malpractice. There is a need to explore alternative strategies that promote critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills, and modify the curriculum to reflect the needs of the 21st century. Specifically, this study seeks to investigate the extent to which critical thinking and curriculum modification can be employed as strategies for eradicating examination malpractice in Nigeria’s educational system.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to examine critical thinking and curriculum modification:

medium of eradicating examination malpractice in Nigeria education system

Hypotheses

H01: There is no significant influence of critical thinking on examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system.

H02: There is no significant influence of curriculum modification on examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system.

H03: There is no significant influence of teachers and parents on examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system.

Methodology

The study examined the influence critical thinking and curriculum modification: medium of eradicating examination malpractice in Nigeria education system. The study employed survey research design. The research instrument adapted for the study were Titled critical thinking and curriculum

modification as medium of eradicating examination malpractice in Nigeria educational system Rating Scale (CTCMEMNES). The instruments consist of twenty (20) items. The sample for the study comprises of 317 respondents that are male and female under age 16 and above. One hundred and five (105) from South South Region, One hundred and Six (106) from South East and One hundred and Six (106) One hundred and five (105) from South West. The instrument passed through face and content validity. The purposive sampling techniques was adopted for the study. The data was collected through the questionnaires and were analyzed using ANCOVA.

Analysis of Data/ Results

H01: There is no significant influence of critical thinking on examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system.

Table 1: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) showing influence of critical thinking on examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	3.546 ^a	3	1.182	23.618	.000	.288
Intercept	7.810	1	7.810	156.082	.000	.469
Critical Thinking	2.611	1	2.611	52.171	.000	.228
Curriculum Modification	.035	1	.035	.705	.402	.004
Teachers, Parents influence	1.629	1	1.629	32.546	.000	.155
Error	8.857	313	.028			
Total	322.000	317				
Corrected Total	12.403	316				

R Squared = .286 (Adjusted R Squared = .274)

Table 1 revealed that there was a significant influence of critical thinking on examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system. ($F_{(2, 23)} = 52.171$; $p > 0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = .228$). The indicated the effect size of 03.2%.

This means that 03.2% of the total 27% variation observed (Adjusted $R^2 = .274$) on critical thinking post-treatment scores on examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system this ANCOVA

model was due to the significant main effect of the treatment. Therefore, hypothesis 1 was rejected. It means that critical thinking does not eradicate examination malpractice in Nigeria education system

H02: There is no significant influence of curriculum modification on examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system.

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) showing influence of curriculum modification on examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	3.546 ^a	3	1.182	23.618	.000	.288
Intercept	7.810	1	7.810	156.082	.000	.469
Critical Thinking	2.611	1	2.611	52.171	.000	.228
Curriculum Modification	.035	1	.035	.705	.402	.004
Teachers, Parents influence	1.629	1	1.629	32.546	.000	.155
Error	8.857	313	.028			
Total	322.000	317				
Corrected Total	12.403	316				

R Squared = .286 (Adjusted R Squared = .274)

In hypothesis 2, it was revealed that curriculum modification was significantly predict examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system. ($F_{(1, 24)} = .705$; $p < 0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = .004$). Therefore, hypothesis 2 was not upheld. This means curriculum modification was

significantly predict examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system.

H03: There is no significant influence of teachers and parents on examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) showing influence of teachers and parents on examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	3.546 ^a	3	1.182	23.618	.000	.288
Intercept	7.810	1	7.810	156.082	.000	.469
Critical Thinking	2.611	1	2.611	52.171	.000	.228
Curriculum Modification	.035	1	.035	.705	.402	.004
Teachers, Parents influence	1.629	1	1.629	32.546	.000	.155
Error	8.857	313	.028			
Total	322.000	317				
Corrected Total	12.403	316				

R Squared = .286 (Adjusted R Squared = .274)

In table 3 it also revealed teachers and parents' involvement on examination malpractice in Nigeria education system is significant. ($F_{(2, 23)} = 32.546$; $p > 0.05$, partial $\eta^2 = .155$). Thus, hypothesis 3 was accepted. This indicates teachers and parents influence was significantly predict examination malpractice in Nigeria education system.

Discussion of Findings

Findings revealed that critical thinking does not eradicate examination malpractice in Nigeria education system. This findings was not in line with the finding of Wahyu, Rumansyah, & Arif, (2017) which stated that problem solving improve students creativity thinking. Going by this findings the fact still remain that the readiness of students for learning process stimulate their cognitive domain to an action and whenever learning take place students will not go does far to engage in any examination malpractice before and during any examination.

Also, the finding revealed that curriculum modification was significantly predict examination malpractice eradication in Nigeria education system. Looking at the finding, one would conclude that students' involvement in examination malpractice is as a result of failure in curriculum upgrading. The curriculum that supposed to be upgraded from time to time to accommodate new innovation of teaching and learning process were not given to the curriculum experts to work on and this seriously affect our educational system in Nigeria. Twiningsih & Elisanti (2021) finding support this finding that introduction of technology into teaching and learning process improve students' performance meaning that students that are

well prepare for an examination will not involve in examination malpractice.

Lastly, the finding revealed that teachers and parents influencing examination malpractice in Nigeria education. This contradict the finding of Renatovna & Renatovna, (2021) which stated that the role of teachers and parents in students achievement is to provide enabling ground for social relations and the development of critical thinking. When these is done the involvement of students in examination malpractice will be stop completely.

Conclusion

Putting an end to examination malpractice in Nigeria is the responsibility of all stake holder in educational system. The students in our institution of learning should not see examination as a medium of obtaining certificate alone but rather to see it as an evaluation instrument to instill creativity skills that is needed for self-reliance and sustainability.

Recommendation

To this end, the following were recommended:

1. Students should not see examination as means of acquire skills
2. Students should not involve in any form examination malpractice tannish their image
3. Students should be well prepared before sitting for any examination
4. Government should always enforce examination rule and regulation on any student find wanting
5. Parents and teachers should caution themselves on their involvement in examination malpractice.

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